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Introduction

The Centre for Environmental Data Analysis (CEDA) is based at the STFC Rutherford Appleton Laboratory. CEDA operates 4 environmental data centres (JASMIN), and professional data analysis environments (JASMIN), and professional data management services for the UK academic community to ensure the availability of stored data for the future.

<http://www.ceda.ac.uk>

New Data

New data which has been added to the CEDA archive.
Sentinel 1A and 1B – SAR data (Interferometric Wide (IW), Extra Wide (EW). Ground range detected (GRD), Single Look Complex (SLC) and Stripmap (SM) products.)
Sentinel 2A (2B to come online shortly) – MSI
Sentinel 3A – SLSTR available on the archive, OLCI and SRAL expected shortly.
ESA CCI – ESA Climate Change Initiative data products.

Data at CEDA

Data

CEDA hold nearly 4 petabytes of environmental data. The majority of which are freely available for academic researchers to access.

Data Centres

CEDA run some of the NERC datacentres covering the areas:

- **Earth Observation** – Data from aircraft and satellite platforms.
- **Atmospheric Science** – Climate and numerical weather prediction model output and observations from aircraft, balloons and ground based instruments.
- **Solar-Terrestrial Physics** – Space weather data from upper atmospheric sounders, solar observatories and interplanetary probes.

Data Search

Search the datasets held by CEDA:
<http://catalogue.ceda.ac.uk/>

Data Access

Many ways to access to the data provided by CEDA: ftp, JASMIN/CEMS and through http via the new CEDA data server built on OpenDAP.

New CEDA data server:

<http://data.ceda.ac.uk/>

Help documentation

New help pages to help with the many aspects of the services that CEDA provide.

New CEDA help pages:

<http://help.ceda.ac.uk/>

JASMIN (academic CEMS)

High performance, high volume data analysis environment for the UK environmental science community.

- 16 PB high performance fast storage
- ~5000 cores
- High performance network design
- Private cloud, to enable flexible usage.
- Group workspace for easy project data sharing.

Academic CEMS – Climate and Environment Monitoring from Space, allocated resource for UK EO on JASMIN

Sentinel data at CEDA

- CEDA are providing a UK mirror archive for the Sentinel satellite series.
- Currently we have downloaded nearly 1400TB of Sentinel data (some data now on our near line tape archive).

- Data is available from 2014 for the first Sentinel satellite Sentinel 1A.

NCEO Data Archive

- CEDA is the designated archive for NCEO:
 - **Preservation** and **Dissemination** of NCEO data products
 - Share, make available and publish data.
- CEDA can assign DOI's (Digital Object Identifiers) to datasets:
 - Required by some journals
 - **Scientific credit** goes to the data producer.

Contact Us

For any queries on any of the datasets or services that CEDA provides then please contact our helpdesk:

Email: support@ceda.ac.uk